

PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEMS OF IMPROVING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract: In this article, scientific research on the organization of the educational process in preschool educational institutions is analyzed, and the issues of directing it to the individuality of children in order to further improve this process are highlighted.

Key words: preschool education, innovative, method, technology, individualization of education, thinking, educational trajectory.

During the past period, effective preschool education aimed at bringing up the young generation growing up in our country healthy and mature in all aspects, introducing effective forms and methods into the educational process, and promoting innovative ideas system organization is one of our important tasks. At the same time, the conducted analysis, ensuring coverage of children with preschool education, filling organizations with educational and methodical materials and fiction, attracting qualified pedagogues and management personnel to the field, introducing innovative technologies in the educational process shows the need to solve the issues of education.¹ The effective implementation of these tasks imposes a huge responsibility on educators, methodologists and psychologists working in preschool education organizations.

Providing modern education to children from preschool age, active development of them mentally, intellectually and socially is one of the urgent issues that need to be solved in preschool education organizations today.

DISCUSSION.

Currently, scientific researchers are dedicated to the research of the theoretical foundations of pedagogical and corrective activities in the elimination of defects in the language development of children of preschool age. In addition, the problem of speech development of children of senior and preparatory groups and elementary school students of general and special educational institutions before school on the basis of folk games was studied. For this purpose, examples of children's games performed in collaboration with songs were selected from our ancient and rich folklore heritage, the classification of games, their place in education, as well as the characteristics

and methods of use in logopedic-corrective work were proposed. Such games play an important role in children's verbal, physical, psychological, and spiritual development.

The problems of formation and development of mathematical thinking in pupils of pre-school educational institutions were researched. In their research, the researchers studied the ways, means and pedagogical conditions of forming the first knowledge of arithmetic and geometry in children of preschool age. He determined that the formation and development of mathematical knowledge in children is one of the important factors in their mental development, self-awareness, and socialization. He especially recognized the importance of the computer environment in organizing interactive logical-mathematical education for children. The child's virtual dialogue with the computer through intermediary characters "animates" the computer and ensures that the child's actions are active and conscious.

It is devoted to the study of the problem of determining the pedagogical possibilities of spiritual and moral upbringing of children in the family by means of Allah. The researcher interpreted the socio-ideological content of Allah, its educational impact, and the etymological meaning and historical formation of the word "Allah" from a pedagogical point of view. Analyzing the philosophical, pedagogical and psychological situation of spiritual and moral education of children by the means of Allah, he classified the types of Allah aimed at spiritual and moral education according to the didactic content of children according to their age, psychological and spiritual development. In addition, on the basis of the cooperation between "family-neighborhood-preschool educational institution", the social-pedagogical mechanism of increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and moral education of children by means of Allah has been improved, and the method of moral and moral education of children by means of Allah has been improved. scientific-methodical recommendations aimed at increasing efficiency have been developed.

We can admit that the problem of improving pedagogical processes in preschool educational institutions has also been researched. He described the specific features and pedagogical-psychological possibilities of the systematic approach in the improvement of pedagogical processes in preschool educational organizations, based the model of improving these processes based on the systematic approach theoretically and empirically. The model of the improvement of the pedagogical process is the mutual integration of the components of educational activity with the areas of development, the provision of reflexive coherence, and the organizational and pedagogical conditions for the

development of independent activity are based on the integrative-variational programs of the formation of basic competencies in the areas of development in children. improved on the basis of prioritizing creativity in its activities.

Since it is important to take into account the characteristics and needs of children with their own characteristics when creating a developmental environment in preschool educational organizations, the leading activity of children of this age is play. In a properly organized game, conditions are created for the development of the child's physical, mental and personal qualities, the formation of readiness for educational activities and the social success of the preschool child, he concludes.

Based on the above scientific activities, research, it can be concluded as follows:

1. During preschool childhood, qualities such as the foundations of individuality as a human being are formed and developed in a child - creative and figurative thinking, imitation of others (often adults), control of one's own behavior and "social" feeling.

2. In preschool childhood, the most active point of children's development corresponds to the period up to the age of 5-6. Therefore, the educational process should be focused on their individuality and the peculiarities of cognitive mechanisms should be taken into account.

3. Accelerating the process of education and upbringing of children from a technical point of view, although it seems to speed up the process of their entry into the ranks of adults, it increases the possibility of slowing down the process of normal mental development.

As a conclusion, we can note that one of the solutions to the problem of improving the educational process in preschool educational organizations is, first of all, the implementation of innovative methods of teaching and training - the path to the educational process and the individuality of the student. is the use of innovative technologies of directed teaching in the educational process.

Teaching children in preschool educational organizations based on interactive didactic games and materials allows to organize education focused on the personality of the child. Such educational activities arouse great interest in children, logical and creative thinking develops without excessive stress during the game, the skills of social activity and compliance with moral standards are cultivated, the natural and social environment is right. perceptions about it are regulated and the correct formation of concepts is ensured. For this, in teaching preschool children, the educator should focus on what they can do with the help and guidance of adults, not on their own.

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